

RoBERTa with LIME for Organic and Inorganic Reaction Classification

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Abstract

The classification of chemical reactions into organic and inorganic types is an important task in cheminformatics and chemical education. In this work, we introduce a new dataset of chemical reactions and evaluate both traditional machine learning models and transformer-based models for classification. Random Forest, SVM, and Logistic Regression achieved moderate performance, while ChemBERTa and RoBERTa provided stronger results. Among these, RoBERTa achieved the highest accuracy of 90%, which is better than ChemBERTa and traditional models. To enhance transparency, we applied Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME) for explainable AI, which highlighted reaction components influencing predictions. This contribution provides both high-performing models and interpretable outputs, making it a valuable step toward intelligent chemical reaction classification systems. Future work will focus on extending the dataset and generating chemical structure visualizations for deeper understanding.

Keywords: Chemical reaction classification, machine learning, deep learning, transformers, RoBERTa, Explainable AI.

1 Introduction

Chemical reaction classification plays a crucial role in both understanding and predicting chemical behavior in scientific and industrial applications. Accurate analysis of chemical reactions is the basis of organic chemistry, computer aided drug design, and many other studies [1]. Therefore, automation classifications of chemical reactions, either organic or inorganic, are essential for analysis. Because the manual approach of chemical reaction type is time-consuming and needs topic experts. In this study, we present a novel chemical reaction compound dataset to identify the reaction type, such as organic or inorganic. For this work, we explore both traditional machine

learning models and transformer models such as random forest classifier, Support Vector Machine (SVM), logistic regression, RoBERTa, and ChemBERTa. Among all the models, we found that RoBERTa model gave comparatively better performance than other models. For the model evaluation, we used classification report, confusion matrix, ROC curve, AUC score, and precision-recall curve. We also used LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations) for the model explainability and transparency.

There are several number of recent studies based on the automation of chemical reaction classifications. Heid & Gree developed a reaction GCNN model using the Condensed Graph of Reaction (CGR) representation, enabling accurate prediction of reaction properties such as activation energies, enthalpies, rate constants, and yields [2]. Wei et al. developed a neural network for organic reaction prediction that achieved 85% accuracy on a test set [3]. Qian et al., introduced BEC-Pred, a BERT-based model that predicts enzyme commission (EC) numbers from reaction SMILES, achieving 91.6% accuracy score [4]. Segler & Waller developed a deep neural network trained on 3.5 million reactions and achieved 97% accuracy in reaction prediction [5]. Chen & Li proposed a deep learning model for reaction condition prediction, achieving 73% top-10 accuracy for solvents and 89% accuracy for temperatures within ± 20 °C [6]. Hou and Dong proposed an explainable coarse-fine level reaction representation model with probabilistic data augmentation on reaction classification and yield prediction tasks [7]. Wang et al., developed a BERT-autoencoder model for large-scale reaction classification on the USPTO TPL dataset, achieving 99.38% accuracy [8]. Qiao et al. introduced multitask transformer models RFRPT and MFRPT for low-resource reaction prediction, achieving top-1 accuracies of 76.9% and 79.8% [9].

The motivation of this study arises from the increasing demand for automatic classification of chemical reactions because it’s difficult to manually understand the chemical reaction and its type. Though several works addressed this problem but those have lack of explainability of the work. Therefore, we aim to bridge this gap by using a dataset and exploring both traditional machine learning and transformer-based models for automated reaction classification, including LIME explainability. The contributions of this research are:

- (i) Comparative analysis by using traditional machine learning models such as Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Logistic Regression, and transformer-based models such as RoBERTa and ChemBERTa.
- (ii) Applied LIME method to make the model’s decisions easier to understand and more transparent for chemists.

The remaining part of this study organize into several key sections. In section II describe about the methodologies, section III experimental results, section IV comparative analysis, and section V conclusion. Also, a reference section added at the end of the study.

2 Methodologies

Fig. 1 Workflow Diagram.

Figure 1 presents the workflow diagram of the full methodology section. The methodology section divided into four key subsections such as dataset analysis, preprocessing and feature engineering, traditional ML models, Transformer models, and model evaluations and explainable AI.

2.1 Dataset Analysis, Preprocessing, and Feature Engineering

For this study, used a dataset containing 301 rows and 2 columns was used, including balanced chemical reactions and their types, such as organic or inorganic [10].

Figure 2 presents the chemical reactions visualization where (a), (b), and (c) are organic compounds and (d) inorganic compound. Each of the chemical compounds contains an input and an output part and we ensure the balanced between input and output.

Table 1 shows the sample of the dataset. In the dataset, organic samples are 162,

Fig. 2 Sample Chemical Reaction Visualizations

Table 1 Chemical Reactions and Their Types

Chemical Reaction	Reaction Type
$2\text{KClO}_3 \longrightarrow 2\text{KCl} + 3\text{O}_2$	Inorganic
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7 \longrightarrow \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{N}_2 + 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Inorganic
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_4 + \text{HBr} \longrightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{Br}$	Organic
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \longrightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$	Organic

and inorganic samples are 139. In these two classes, we contain several types of reactions such as reduction, decomposition, addition, chain, combustion, redox, etc. In the dataset preprocessing, removed null values and duplicates. Then, developed preprocessing function that converted arrow symbols (\rightarrow) to standardized text representations \rightarrow , gas evolution symbols (\uparrow) as gas, precipitate symbols (\downarrow) as precipitate, and converted all text into lowercase. After that, we used label encoding to convert the categorical target variable, organic or inorganic, into numerical format where inorganic is 0 and organic as 1. The dataset was split into 80% for training and 20% for testing purposes. We also used Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) vectorization to convert the preprocessed chemical reaction text into numerical features for the traditional ML models purposes. In the TF-IDF method, include 5,000 features as maximum, N-gram range of 1-3, minimum frequency 2, etc.

For the experimental setup, we used Kaggle notebook environment with GPU P-100, Google Colab. We also used several standard Python library for model implement and visualizations [13-14].

2.2 Traditional ML Models

In this research, we implemented three traditional machine learning models such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest Classifier, Logistics regression. We also used Grid search CV as hyperparameter tuning using 5-fold cross-validation within each of the model. For the Support Vector Machine (SVM), we tried different kernels, including linear, RBF, and polynomial. We also used different regularization parameter C such as 0.1, 1, 10, 100, gamma values such as scale, auto, 0.001, and 0.01, and balanced class weights to handle any class imbalance [11]. The best SVM configuration was an RBF kernel with C=10, gamma=0.01, and balanced class weights. For the Random Forest model, we experimented with the number of trees such as 100, 200, 300, max depth, and minimum samples split [12]. The best setup was 100 trees with a maximum depth of 20 and balanced class weights. Finally, for Logistic Regression, we used L1, L2, and elastic net regularization, and optimized the regularization strength. The optimal configuration was L2 regularization with C=1 and balanced class weights.

2.3 Transformer Models

We implemented a RoBERTa-based sequence classification model using the pre-trained 'roberta-base' model [15]. The model was configured as binary classification, dropout 0.3 for regularization. Optimizer as Adam with learning rate 2e-5, and weight decay as 0.01. We also used ChemBERTa, a specialized transformer model pre-trained on chemical data [16]. For this transformer model, we used similar parameters as the RoBERTa model. Both of the models training was performed for 20 epochs with a batch size of 16 on an NVIDIA GPU P-100 on Kaggle environment. Both models were evaluated using accuracy, F1-score, precision, recall, confusion matrix, AUC and LIME explainability. After that based on the comparative analysis of all models, we found RoBERTa models perform better than the others.

2.4 Model Evaluation and Explainable AI

We evaluated all models using multiple metrics to analyze each of the models performance correctly. We calculate the accuracy score, precision, recall, and f1-score based on the equation 1, 2, 3, 4. Here, TP refers to True Positive, TN as True Negative, FP as False Positive, and FN as False Negative.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (4)$$

We also analysis model performance using confusion matrix, ROC curve, AUC score, and precision-recall curve. Each model was evaluated separately for organic and inorganic reactions for class wise analysis. We implemented Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME) to understand the features each model used for predictions [17]. For the LIME build a function which randomly select 10 chemical reactions and shows the explainability each of them. LIME shows the parts of chemical reaction influenced for the class predictions and highlights the key chemical compounds and reaction components.

3 Experimental Results

The results show that RoBERTa model achieved highest accuracy score which is 90%. ChemBERTa model achieved 77%, SVM 78.69%, random forest classifier 83.61%, and logistics regression model 81.97%. Among both traditional and transformer model RoBERTa shows the best performance.

Table 2 Class-wise Performance Metrics of RoBERTa Model

Metrics	Organic	Inorganic
Precision	0.92	0.88
Recall	0.85	0.93
F1-Score	0.88	0.91
ROC AUC	0.97	0.97
PR AUC	0.96	0.98

In the experimental results, Table 2 and 3 show the RoBERTa model class-wise performance and classification report. Table II reports Organic reactions achieving 0.92 precision and 0.85 recall, while Inorganic reactions have 0.88 precision and 0.93 recall. F1-scores are high for both classes,

0.88 for Organic and 0.91 for Inorganic. Also shows that ROC AUC and PR AUC are above 0.96. Table III summarizes the classification report, showing overall accuracy of 0.90 and balanced precision, recall, and F1-scores for both classes. Table IV shows that the ChemBERTa model performance, with Organic reactions having 0.73 precision and 0.79 recall, and Inorganic reactions 0.81 precision and 0.76 recall. The overall accuracy of ChemBERTa is 0.77. Table V shows the Random Forest model performed better, with Inorganic reactions having 0.80 precision and 0.86 recall, and Organic reactions 0.87 precision and 0.82 recall. The overall accuracy of Random Forest is 0.836.

The confusion matrix of Figure 3, shows that most of the samples were correctly classified where 24 for inorganic and 31 for organic. Only a few were misclassified, such as 4 for inorganic as organic and 2 for organic as inorganic. Figure 4, the ROC curve

Table 3 Comparison of Classification Reports Across Models

Class / Metric	Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Organic	RoBERTa	0.92	0.86	0.89
	ChemBERTa	0.73	0.79	0.76
	Random Forest	0.87	0.82	0.84
Inorganic	RoBERTa	0.89	0.94	0.91
	ChemBERTa	0.81	0.76	0.78
	Random Forest	0.80	0.86	0.83
Accuracy	RoBERTa	0.90		
	ChemBERTa	0.77		
	Random Forest	0.836		

Fig. 3 Confusion Matrix of RoBERTa Model

shows model performance for both organic and inorganic classes, with a high AUC of 0.973. It represents almost perfect classification between organic and inorganic classes.

Fig. 4 ROC Curve and AUC Score of RoBERTa Model

Figure 5 shows the Precision-Recall curve where AUC for organic is 0.963 and for inorganic is 0.982, showing the model is very accurate in both cases. Figure 6, the LIME explanation shows the model prediction as Inorganic with 78% probability. Important words like nh4 clo3, n2, 2h2o, and cl2 influenced the prediction. The highlighted words show which parts of the reaction contributed most to classifying it as Inorganic. Also, Figure 7 shows the same thing for the Organic class. Here, both Figures 6 and 7 true prediction and model prediction are correct, which represent the model's transparency and accurate prediction between the classes.

4 Comparative Analysis

According to Table 4, we compared the RoBERTa model performance among several traditional ML models and ChemBERTa model. Among compared all of these models our model shows better performance. Table 5 represents the ML models performances using accuracy score, precision, recall, and f1-score. Among the traditional model random forest classifier model shows better performance.

Fig. 5 Precision and Recall Curve of RoBERTa Model

Table 4 Model Accuracy Comparison

Model	Accuracy (%)
SVM	78.69
Random Forest Classifier	83.61
Logistic Regression	81.97
ChemBERTa	77
RoBERTa (Best Model)	90

Table 5 Overall Performance Metrics of Traditional ML Models

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
SVM	0.7869	0.7876	0.7895	0.7867
Random Forest	0.8361	0.8355	0.8377	0.8357
Logistic Regression	0.8197	0.8252	0.8252	0.8197

True: Inorganic, Predicted: Inorganic
Reaction: $\text{nh}_4\text{clo}_3 \rightarrow \text{n}_2 + 2\text{h}_2\text{o} + \text{cl}_2$

LIME Explanation:

Prediction probabilities

Inorganic

Organic

Text with highlighted words

nh₄clo₃ -| **n₂** + **2h₂o** + **cl₂**

Fig. 6 LIME for Inorganic Class

True: Organic, Predicted: Organic
Reaction: $\text{c}_2\text{h}_2 + \text{br}_2 + \text{h}_2\text{o} \rightarrow \text{c}_2\text{h}_2\text{broh}$

LIME Explanation:

Prediction probabilities

Inorganic

Organic

Text with highlighted words

c₂h₂ + **br₂** + **h₂o** -| **c₂h₂broh**

Fig. 7 LIME for Organic Class

5 Conclusion

In this study, we used a dataset of chemical reactions and classified them into organic and inorganic types. After that, we used a comparative analysis of using both traditional machine learning models and transformer-based models. Experimental results showed that the RoBERTa model achieved the best performance with 90% accuracy, which is better than traditional models and ChemBERTa. Moreover, we applied LIME for explainability, making the model’s predictions more transparent and interpretable for chemists, which is often missing in earlier works. Limitations of this work are that the dataset size is small, which may not fully capture the extensive diversity and complexity inherent in the global landscape of chemical reactions. For future work, we plan to extend the dataset to not only classify chemical reactions but also describe the chemicals and generate their visual structures. This is important because text-based reactions alone are not always sufficient for interpretation, and visual representation will make chemical understanding more effective for researchers, students, and practitioners.

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